

ELIXIR Onboarding Protocol: Recommendations and Guidelines

This document provides recommendations for implementing onboarding practices within ELIXIR Nodes. Based on an analysis of practices across six Nodes (CH, DE, ES, FR, IE, PT) obtained between mid January and mid February 2025, the document outlines key recommendations that offer flexibility to accommodate each Node's resources and strategic needs.

Practical Guidelines for designing an Onboarding strategy

This guide outlines different formats and key considerations to ensure an effective integration of new members in your Node. Before proceeding in the design of your onboarding strategy, it is important to have a comprehensive knowledge of your Node, such as understanding the structure and organisation of your Node, eligibility of the Node members, career stage and role of the Node members being onboarded, and other essential factors. The protocol can be adapted based on Node size and resources, Node geographical distribution, language requirements, specific role requirements, available technology, and cultural considerations.

Below, you can find an initial list of key aspects that a Node can choose from based on its specific needs. While these elements are flexible, it is essential to consider them to ensure a well-planned onboarding process.

Onboarding format:

- Welcome email with onboarding content
- Onboarding meeting (in person or online)
- Resources in a shared space
- Mentoring program

Types of meetings:

- Individualised meeting
- One-on-one mentoring sessions
- Webinar
- Group meeting

- Q&A sessions
- Roundtable discussions

Alternatively to meetings, Nodes can also prepare recorded sessions to be used asynchronously.

Periodicity:

- One-time onboarding
- On-demand onboarding
- Regular scheduled onboarding meetings
- Back-to-back event with a node relevant event/workshop
- Follow-up meetings/emails to the previous options

Language requirements:

- Node's local language
- English
- Sign languages
- Multilingual support

Contents shared based on target audience:

- General information to any role in the Node
- Role-specific information, i.e. Node Coordinator
- Tailored to onboard in a part of the structure, i.e. specific Platform, Community
- Adapted to the career stage or job position/title, i.e. PhD students, software developers

Scope of the content:

- ELIXIR as a pan-European distributed Research Infrastructure
- ELIXIR Node specific overview
- Institution overview
- Research group overview

Commonly used Onboarding formats

Among all the onboarding formats, we will focus on welcome emails and meetings, which are two common practices currently adopted by the Nodes. These formats are essential for supporting new members to integrate into their Node and in the ELIXIR environment.

Welcome email with onboarding content

For cases where onboarding is conducted through a welcome email with onboarding content, below is a set of recommendations to ensure that the information is clear, engaging, and provides a strong foundation for new members. It is recommended to keep the information minimal but adding links to relevant documents and resources. These can be customized based on the Node's specific needs.

1. Welcome

- Welcome from a relevant Node member

2. Brief introduction

- Information of the Node at the national level and also in the context of ELIXIR
- Link relevant documents and resources where the information is expanded: ELIXIR Website, Node website, resources, etc.

3. Practical Information

- Communication channels
- Key contacts
- Inform of future Node events, if any
- [Glossary of terms](#)

4. Wrap-up and next steps

- Follow-up actions (e.g. joining meetings, complete documents, etc.)

Onboarding meeting

For cases where the onboarding is conducted through a meeting, below is a series of recommendations to ensure a smooth and engaging experience. These can be adapted according to the Node's needs.

1. Welcome and Introduction

- Welcome from a relevant Node member
- Round of introductions
- Meeting objectives

2. ELIXIR Overview

- ELIXIR structure and mission
- Scientific Programme, cross-node collaborations and relevant projects

3. Node-specific overview:

- Node structure, mission and strategy
- Node's role at national level and in relation to ELIXIR
- Node triangle and other main contacts
- Portfolio of resources
- Projects involvement
- Industry and international stakeholders

4. Practical Information

- Link relevant documents where the information is expanded: ELIXIR Website, Node website, ELIXIR Handbook of Operations, and other resources.
- Communication channels
- Relevant contacts

5. Interactive Session

- Q&A

6. Wrap-up

- Summary of key points
- Use the feedback mechanism that has been chosen
- Follow-up actions

Good Practices for meeting's success

This section provides practical tips to ensure that onboarding meetings are engaging, effective, and well-structured, helping to optimize the experience for new members.

1. Pre-meeting:

- Send agenda and materials in advance
- Collect preliminary questions
- Confirm technical requirements
- Share relevant documentation
- Decide meeting duration (e.g., 60min, 90 min)
- In person / on-line / hybrid (depending on geographical distribution and available technology)

2. During meeting:

- Encourage active participation
- Use real examples and use cases

- Include different level of experienced Node members

3. Post-meeting:

- Share meeting summary and resources
- Schedule follow-ups
- Use the feedback mechanism that has been chosen
- Ongoing support availability on demand
- Connection to relevant groups on demand

Templates and Resources

This section lists suggested materials and resources that can be used to support a smooth and efficient onboarding process. These tools help Nodes standardize key aspects while allowing for customization based on specific needs.

1. Email Templates - to be designed by the Nodes, such as:

- Initial welcome
- Meeting invitation
- Follow-up communication
- Resource sharing

2. Checklists - to be designed by the Nodes, such as:

- Pre-onboarding preparation
- Meeting organization
- Post-onboarding actions
- Documentation requirements

3. Presentation Templates and other resources:

- ELIXIR slide deck
- Node-specific information and slides
- Role-specific guidance
- Relevant links to share: [ELIXIR web](#), Node web, and others
- [ELIXIR Handbook of operations](#)

Feedback mechanisms

Designing a feedback strategy will ensure a structured approach to gathering, analyzing, and defining correction measures to improve the onboarding practices. By continuously refining the onboarding process, it enhances the experience, effectiveness and impact of new members integration.

1. Feedback collection methods

- Anonymous post-onboarding surveys
- Informal check-ins after 1 (or more) month
- Structured feedback sessions after 3-6 months

2. Key metrics to track

- Participation rates
- Demographic information from the participants
- Satisfaction levels
- Areas requiring clarification or further information/resources
- Engagement in Node activities and ELIXIR activities

3. Implementation of feedback

- Regular updates to processes and materials
- Annual comprehensive review, or according to the periodicity of the Node onboarding practices